

23. Interesting observations on the numbers of partial orders and transitive relations

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Abstract

The Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS) is a database of over 3,20,000 integer sequences. For many of these integer sequences, there is neither a known counting formula nor a generating function. Two such sequences are the sequence A006905 of the number of transitive relations and the sequence A001035 of the number of partial orders. In this short note, some recursive relations are obtained for A001035 analogous to those obtained for A006905 in [1].

Introduction

Let S be a non-empty set. Any subset R of $S \times S$ is a relation on S . A relation R on S is a partial order if and only if

- (a) $(x, x) \in R, \forall x \in S$
- (b) $(x, y) \in R \Rightarrow (y, x) \in R, \forall x, y \in S$
- (c) $(x, y), (y, z) \in R \Rightarrow (x, z) \in R, \forall x, y, z \in S$

That is R is a partial order on S if and only if R is reflexive, anti-symmetric and transitive. Let $A = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$. The number of reflexive relations on A is given by $2^{n(n-1)}$. The number of symmetric relations on A is given by $2^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}$. The number of anti-symmetric relations on A is given by $2^n 3^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}$. Unlike the enumeration of reflexive relations, symmetric relations and anti-symmetric relations, the enumeration of transitive relations and that of partial orders is very difficult and has evaded all the attempts thus far.

The Main Discussion

The problem of enumerating partial orders is very closely connected to the problem of enumerating transitive relations on a set. In fact, if $t(n)$ denotes

the number of transitive relations on a set with n elements and P_n denotes the number of partial orders on the set, then

$$t(n) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \quad (1)$$

where $\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}$ denotes Sterling numbers of the second kind [2]. This brings to light the fact that since the problem of enumerating partial orders on a set is an open problem, so is that of enumerating transitive relations on a set. This is the precise reason why OEIS enlists both $t(n)$ and P_n for the same values of n that is for $n \leq 18$. The known values of P_n and $t(n)$ that are available in OEIS are tabulated as under [3].

n	No.ofpartialorders,P_n	No.oftransitiverelations,$t(n)$
0	1	1
1	1	2
2	3	13
3	19	171
4	219	3994
5	4231	154303
6	130023	9415189
7	6129859	878222530
8	431723379	122207703623
9	44511042511	24890747921947
10	6611065248783	7307450299510288
11	1396281677105899	3053521546333103057
12	414864951055853499	1797003559223770324237
13	171850728381587059351	1476062693867019126073312
14	98484324257128207032183	1679239558149570229156802997
15	77567171020440688353049939	2628225174143857306623695576671
16	834805297854901578138442565 79	5626175867513779058707006016592 954
17	12215254125029532286294128126 9151	1638827071336486394379197986683 8296851

18	2419393925972011766028978201 48085023	646627208469085427946788597182 27127212465
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Let $n = n_1 + n_2$. In [1], the following recursive relations were obtained for $t(n)$, the number of transitive relations on n elements.

$$t(n) > t(n_1)t(n_2) \quad (2)$$

$$t(n) > t(n_1)t(n_2) + (2^{n_1} - 1)t(n_2) + (2^{n_2} - 1)t(n_1) \quad (3)$$

$$t(n) > t(n_1)t(n_2) + t(n_2) \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n_1} \binom{n_1}{r} t(n_1 - r) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$+ t(n_1) \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n_2} \binom{n_2}{r} t(n_2 - r) \right]$$

$$t(n) > 3 \times t(n - 1) + 2 \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{r} t(n-1-r) \right] \quad (5)$$

Using these, we obtain the following analogous recursive relations for P_n , the number of partial orders on n elements.

Theorem 1: Let $n = n_1 + n_2$. The following holds:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k > \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \quad (6)$$

Proof: Using (1) in (2), (6) follows immediately.

Theorem 2: Let $n = n_1 + n_2$. The following holds:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k > \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) + (2^{n_1} - 1) \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \\ + (2^{n_2} - 1) \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \quad (7)$$

Proof: Using (1) in (3), (7) follows immediately.

Theorem 3: Let $n = n_1 + n_2$. The following holds:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k > \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) + \\ \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n_2} \binom{n_2}{r} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2-r} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2-r \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right] \\ + \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_2 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) \left[\sum_{r=1}^{n_1} \binom{n_1}{r} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1-r} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n_1-r \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right] \quad (8)$$

Proof: Using (1) in (4), (8) follows immediately.

Theorem 4: Let $n = n_1 + n_2$. The following holds:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k > 3 \times \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n-1 \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right) + 2 \\ \times \left[\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{r} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1-r} \left\{ \begin{matrix} n-1-r \\ k \end{matrix} \right\} P_k \right] \quad (9)$$

Proof: Using (1) in (5), (9) follows immediately.

References:

- [1] Mala, F.A. On the number of transitive relations on a set. Indian J Pure Appl Math (2021). doi.org/10.1007/s13226-021-00100-0
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- [3] OEIS, Sloane, Neil J. A. and The OEIS Foundation Inc., The on-line encyclopedia of integer sequences, 2020